

PERCEIVED LEVEL OF NATIONALISM AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO THEIR ATTITUDE TOWARDS HISTORY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 9

Pages: 1192-1207

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1924

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11673200

Manuscript Accepted: 05-14-2024

Perceived Level of Nationalism among Senior High School Students and its Relationship to their Attitude towards History

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Abstract

Nationalism is the love of one's country and people. This includes pride in one's cultural heritage, support for the country's aspirations, patriotism, and advocacy of national independence. This study aims to determine the level of nationalism among Senior High School students and its relationship to their level of attitude toward history. The research utilized both quantitative and qualitative research designs and conducted the at Saint Mary's University Senior High School with 389 students from STEM, HumSS, ABM, ICT, HE strands and AD Track, utilizing an adopted questionnaire. The respondents' level of nationalism achieved a mean interpreted as high, likewise, a favorable interpretation for level of attitude towards history. The result also indicates a significant difference in the respondent's level of nationalism in terms of sex, strands, and grade level; and level of attitude towards history with strands. However, there is a no significant difference in terms of ethnicity, as such for level of attitude towards history in terms of sex, grade level and ethnicity. Moreover, there is a moderate positive correlation between the respondents' level of nationalism and attitude towards history. Furthermore, the respondents have a high patriotic sentiment in strengthening their sense of nationalism. This research serves as a valuable contribution to understanding and instilling a sense of nationalism among the youth with history as its companion.

Keywords: *history, national pride, national belonging, patriotic sentiments*

Introduction

The youth are agents of change as a group that has a great opportunity to make changes to their country. Dr. Jose P. Rizal emphasized, "The youths are the hope of the nation." It is crucial for each upcoming generation to possess a profound commitment to nationalism, as they are the architects of prospective society. The study of Baron (2022) indicates that today's youth stay locked in the past since they often demonstrate a nationalistic mindset.

Nationalism is the love of one's country and people. It includes pride in one's cultural heritage, support for the country's aspirations, patriotism, and advocacy of national independence. It also involves the belonging of an individual to the nation and its relationship with fellow countrymen. One way to love a country is to know its story by studying history. Nationalism emerged almost simultaneously with the formation of history as a modern discipline (Lim, 2020).

History, on the other hand, is a discipline that studies the chronological record of events (as affecting a nation or people), based on a critical examination of source materials and usually presenting an explanation of their causes, giving an understanding of how events in the past made things the way they were today, respecting the significance of these events in molding nationalism (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2023).

Additionally, Nair et al., (2017), explained that in this modern era, students are found to be lacking in their spirit of nationalism; the youths, especially the senior high school students in today's time, ponder more on the trends set by society, focusing more time on social media platforms. Moreover, Chaiklin (2012) stated that the influence of globalization among students causes the unprepared young generation to lose its national identity. In addition, cultural uniformity in the current era ultimately shifts the identity of each nation (Chaiklin, 2012).

There are existing studies in the Philippines that show a low level of nationalism among Filipino youths. Philippine Journal of Psychology (2019) found that Filipino youths showed a relatively low level of national identity. The study surveyed college students and found that only 25% strongly identified as Filipino, while 27% had a weak sense of national identity. Moreover, Experimental Social Psychology (n.d.) explained that learning about the positive aspects of a country's history can increase feelings of national pride and patriotism. The researchers claimed that participants who read positive historical narratives about their country felt more positive about their nation and expressed more willingness to engage in pro-national behaviors, such as donating money to support the country, respecting the Philippine flag, and singing the national anthem.

Furthermore, the Department of Education (DepEd) also gives importance to how nationalism is always engraved in Filipino youths. DepEd envisions producing learners who are true citizens of the country filled with a strong sense of nationalism, to wit: "We dream of Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation." As such, having an intense will and desire to serve, protect, and work for the country's betterment is one of the primary goals of the state to be instilled in the youth. Studying Philippine history is vital to every individual.

It upholds prior knowledge on how to solve modern issues and innovate domestic products in accordance with the time situated. History serves as a guide for every Filipino from the past, still in the present and future. Educating them about the country's history is a sense of appreciation for the patriotic sentiments of the national heroes. It develops the national identity and strengthens the sense of nationalism.

Republic Act 8491 also known as the Flag and Heraldic Code of the Philippines mandates that every Filipino citizen has the responsibility to love the country. It is intended to revitalize the love of the country and underscore the importance of complying with standard expressions of respect for our national symbols. Nationhood requires that its people approve of forms of expression that symbolize respect, patriotism, and love for the country (Delos Santos et al., 2014).

There have been several studies on nationalism and history conducted abroad, yet there are still insufficient sources in the Philippines. Hence, it serves as the study's gap.

Level of Nationalism

Setiawan (2020) defined nationalism as a situation where one's absolute allegiance to a particular nation or ethnic group forms a political nation. Citizen loyalty to the state is a natural extension of national tolerance and solidarity (culture, language, and ethnicity). A state's nationalism is a way of seeing human society as primarily consisting of discrete, different nations, each with an obvious right to exist and to command loyalty. Nationalism is a kind of national emotion-based ideology; this is the love and loyalty of citizens for the nation itself, including inheritance and maintenance by citizens such as customs, language, and religion. The attitude of nationalism in the context of Indonesian nationalism consists of an awareness of unity to respect and appreciate each other because Indonesia is inhabited by various tribes, cultures, and religions.

Furthermore, Snyder (1990) postulated that nationalism is the state of the psyche, feeling, or assumption dialect, having a writing in which the goals of the country have been communicated, and now and again, having a typical religion. Likewise, Quibera (1996) saw nationalism as a supposition or having a place with a group whose individuals relate to an arrangement of images, convictions, and lifestyles and have the will to settle on their regular political predetermination. Denial (1994) observed that nationalism is a thing of energy and feeling and is subsequently post-judicious and post-general; it is intended to be felt and accepted and not coldly dissected. The definitions that have been proposed to comprehend patriotism incorporate the consistent idea that there is dedication amongst the populace of a given country. The populace of that given country works towards adding to a country that they can call their own, partaking in a typical dialect, having regular convictions, having a basic domain, and having a feeling of having a place. The feeling of having a place suggests that patriotism may be viewed as a sort of social personality.

As indicated, the term nationalism is utilized as a part of two definitions. The principal is that nationalism tries to distinguish a behavioral element, this being the country, and from there on looks to seek after certain political and social objectives for its benefit (Evans et al., 1998). In the second utilization, nationalism is an opinion of steadfastness towards the country, which is shared by the individuals and characterizes nationalism as a dedication to the ethnic gathering (Connor, 1994).

National Pride

National pride serves as an important factor in determining the development of the country. It also acts as a boundary for cultural imperialism threats. National pride requires admiration and interest—the feeling that anyone has some portion of an accomplishment or an admirable characteristic. Moreover, national pride is a positive indicator that the people feel for their nation. Equally, pride and self-esteem are what a person has in him that concerns his nation, and a person derives pride and self-esteem from his national identity (Castillo et al., 2016).

According to the International Social Survey Programme [ISSP] (2010), sources of national pride were (a) sports, the most common source of national pride. Next were (b) arts and literature, (c) history, and (d) science and technology. These four aspects mentioned got a high level of pride among countries. Aspects that got a lower level of national pride were: (d) democracy; (e) the economy; (f) the military; (g) global political influence; (h) the social welfare system; and (g) fair and equal treatment. Domain-specific aspects also assist in identifying the general level of national pride and detecting the elements that are objects of particular pride in each country.

Connection to Countrymen

Smith (1998) demanded the subjective nature of a national character's parts. From a different perspective, the most significant nature of those parts is not whether they are or are not subjective; rather, what makes a difference is whether they are felt as genuine by those sharing a typical character.

Tamir (1995) said that a country is a group whose individuals offer sentiments of a clique, generous peculiarity, and selectiveness, as well as convictions in a typical lineage and persistent parentage. A country is a socially activated group of people, trusting themselves to be united by some arrangement of attributes that separate them (in their own particular personalities) from untouchables, endeavoring to make or keep up their own state; likewise, it broadcasts the country as an entire, which offers intending to their lives, and consequently, it frequently motivates them to act in ways that are conflicting with the requests of formal consistency or instrumental

thinking (Haas, 1986). For the patriot, the country is not a method but rather a significance. The study by Anderson (1983) distinguished the country as an 'envisioned group,' and specified that it is envisioned in light of the fact that individuals from even the smallest country will never know the majority of their colleagues, meet them, or even know about them, yet in the brains of each lives the picture of their unifying fellowship.

National Belonging

Nations generally mean a large group of people who have a sense of belonging in a country. However, the question of race is quite extensive and means that the composite views of people have been highlighted by a number of leading scholars. Issar (2021) stated that civic culture is pluralistic and based on communication and persuasion, a culture of consensus and diversity, a culture that permits change but moderates it.

Overall views expressed by the scholars of many nations around the existence of strong bonds between people, the question of race and ethnicity, language issues, and provincial or territorial matters such as the subjective feeling of the history and ideals shared. As a country that has a plural society (heterogeneous), such as the

Philippines, the main problem is to form a strong bond between the diverse ethnic groups that exist, particularly in the context of realizing the ideals of the nation's building. The intention to build a united nation-state is still a major problem and is hotly debated among scholars and politicians.

Smith (1998), has created the most thorough investigation of the social segments of national personality to date. Values, convictions, traditions, propensities, languages, and practices are transmitted to the new individuals who learn the way of life of a specific country. The procedure of identification with a specific society infers an innumerable amount of enthusiastic speculation ready to encourage solidarity securities among the individuals from a given group who come to perceive each other as kindred nationals (Gellner, 1983).

Level of Attitude Towards History

History is a subject that instills knowledge, attitudes, and values regarding the process of change and development of a society from the past to the present. Learning history in schools needs to be carried out to build a scientific perspective with a time perspective, shared memory, and awareness of the core values of the nation to shape identity. Learning history as an element of the development of cultural nationalism is functioning as a mediation in establishing relations between the elements of society that are pluralistic in nature. Nationalism insight can be applied through history learning in schools. History lessons that implement national insights in historical learning material are very important to instill the attitude of nation and state, which contain many values of accepting and appreciating diversity, tolerance, national unity, national love, and raising awareness of the crisis of solidarity to pluralism, which leads to division so that it can be overcome; these values are part of nationalism (Setiawan, 2020). The youth tend to be sightless about the history of their country. They often ponder doing social media, which results in them wasting more of their time and ignoring the reality that happens in our country.

According to Setiawan (2020), interest in learning history, and national insight with a nationalist attitude interest in learning history is a fixed tendency and an urge to pay attention to learning activities. Learning activities are a way of changing students towards positive things because, when studying a subject, it is expected to be able to think and behave. Learning can make students face their inability to change and think more and more innovatively. Interest in learning is driven by love and interest; it can affect the level and continuity of involvement in learning and the depth of understanding reached by students, in this case in history subjects. Interested in something means that one cares about it and mostly has positive feelings towards it. Feeling happy and interested in studying history makes someone pay high attention to history lessons. Students who are interested will study the material contained in history lessons seriously because there is an attraction for them. The interest in learning history will determine the emergence of feelings of pleasure and attention for students in learning history.

Saint Mary's University Senior High School conducts a monthly flag-raising ceremony in front of the Fr. Godfrey Lambrecht Building, also known as Four Pillars. The institution also holds core subjects integrating history-related topics in all strands such as Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics, and specialized subjects for the Humanities and Social Sciences strand, like Philippine Politics and Governance. However, students are not actively participating during the singing of the national anthem and are not well informed about the country's history. Henceforth, this study aimed to explore the level of nationalism among senior high school students at Saint Mary's University and its relationship to their attitude towards learning Philippine history.

Furthermore, the study examined the students' level of national pride, connection to countrymen, and national belonging; analyzes the students' level of attitude towards history; and determines the significant difference between the respondents' level of nationalism and level of attitude towards history based on sex, strands, grade level, and ethnicity; and investigates the significant relationship between the students' nationalism and their attitude towards history. The results of this paper play a crucial role in comprehending the attitude of senior high school students at Saint Mary's University towards learning history, as well as the effectiveness of the senior high school curriculum and strengthening a sense of nationalism among students.

Besides, the study offers suggestions on how to enhance the teaching of subjects relating to nationalism, such as history, provide recommendations for promoting or reinforcing nationalism among the youth, and encourage and raise awareness about how important

it is to have a nationalist spirit. The relevance of studying history illustrates how deeply a citizen loves his country.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of nationalism among senior high school students at Saint Mary's University and its relationship to their attitude towards history. This paper sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' level of nationalism in terms:
 - 1.1. national pride;
 - 1.2. connection to countrymen; and
 - 1.3. national belonging?
2. What is the respondents' level of attitude towards history?
3. Is there a significant difference on the level of nationalism when the respondents are grouped according to the following:
 - 3.1. sex;
 - 3.2. grade level;
 - 3.3. strand; and
 - 3.4. ethnicity?
4. Is there a significant difference on the level of attitude towards history when the respondents are grouped according to the following:
 - 4.1. sex;
 - 4.2. grade level;
 - 4.3. strand; and
 - 4.4. ethnicity?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of nationalism and level of attitude towards history?
6. What are suggestions on ways to strengthen a sense of nationalism?

Methodology

Research Design

This research used both qualitative and quantitative research design. Furthermore, to compare, and correlate the opinion of the research participants about significant difference in the level of nationalism according to sex, strand, ethnicity, and grade level, and significant relationship of their level of nationalism and level of attitude towards history, this study utilized descriptive-comparative and descriptive-correlational research designs, respectively. Moreover, this paper applied qualitative research through an open-ended question which were thematically analyzed.

Participants

The study included 389 grade 11 and 12 students enrolled in SMU Senior High School for the academic year 2023-2024.

For grade 11, there were nine sections of the STEM strand, two in the HumSS strand, one in ABM, one section of the AD track, ICT, and, HE, respectively. However, in the 12th grade, there were nine sections in STEM, two in HumSS, one in ABM, one section of AD track, ICT and, HE, respectively. Moreover, this study used simple random sampling to determine the sample size of its respondents from the total population.

Table 1 shows the number of participants when grouped by profile variables.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile Variables	n	%
Sex		
Male	165	42.4
Female	224	57.6
Strand		
AT- ABM	57	14.7
AD Track	25	6.4
TVL- HE	21	5.4
AT- HumSS	72	18.5
TVL- ICT	25	6.4
AT- STEM	189	48.6
Grade Level		
Grade 11	186	47.8
Grade 12	203	52.2
Ethnicity		

Gaddang	13	3.3
Ifugao	38	9.8
Ilocano	159	40.9
Isinay	3	.8
Tagalog	94	24.2
Others	14	3.6
Ilocano- Tagalog	34	8.7
Gaddang- Tagalog- Itawes	1	.3
Ifugao- Ilocano- Tagalog	1	.3
Ilocano-Isinay	3	.8
Ifugao- Ilocano	9	2.3
Ifugao- Kankanaey	1	.3
Ifugao- Bontoc	1	.3
Ilocano- Isinay- Tagalog	3	.8
Ifugao- Ilocano- Tagalog- Bicolano	1	.3
Gaddang- Ifugao- Ilocano- Tagalog	2	.5
Gaddang- Ilocano- Cebuano	1	.3
Ifugao- Tagalog	2	.5
Ilokano- Kapampangan	1	.3
Ilocano- Waray	1	.3
Ilocano- Isinay- Pangasinense	1	.3
Gaddang- Ilocano- Tagalog	2	.5
Gaddang-Ilocano	4	1.0
Total	389	100.00%

The majority of responders were female, with 224 responses, while males had 165 responses. This is because female learners dominated the actual enrollment during the institution's current school year; also, data was collected using five strands and one track. The STEM Strand in the Academic Track had the highest number of respondents due to the large number of entrants. There were 203 responses from the 12th grade compared to 186 from the 11th grade. Furthermore, 17 additional ethnicities were listed among the six alternatives on the questionnaires, making Ilocano the dominant ethnic group in SMUSHS.

Instruments

This research utilized an adapted questionnaire developed by Mokhtar, et al. (2016), titled "Characteristics and Level of Nationalism Among Malaysian Youth" in terms of level of nationalism. To get the respondents' attitude towards history, the questionnaire developed by Issar (2021) with a title of "Students' Attitude Towards Studying History and Teaching Practices" was used.

Part I of the research instrument was designed to gather respondents' demographic profiles. It included the items such as their age, sex, grade level, strand, and ethnicity that they belong to. Part II of the research instrument delved on respondents' level of nationalism. It has three (3) subparts: national pride, connection to countrymen and national belonging, and attitude towards History. Part III of the research instrument included the open-ended question.

The interpretation of this table was the analysis of Cronbach's Alpha Score for each of the single dimensions. A final Cronbach's Alpha was computed using the 31 items scale. The score was 0.950. Reliability test was conducted and the result of Cronbach's Alpha was 0.950. The reliability score indicates that the questionnaire is reliable and valid.

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha Result Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.943	.950	31

Procedure

The adapted questionnaires from Issar (2021) and Mokhtar, et al.(2016) were modified by the researchers. It has undergone content validation and checked by the research teacher, adviser, validator and coordinator. After which the researchers incorporated the suggestions and secured a permit through the school principal for the administering of questionnaire to the respondents. Moreover, the research instrument went through reliability testing using SPSS or Statistical Package for Social Sciences resulting in an equivalent

description of acceptable. The results of the gathered and tabulated data were discussed in Chapter 3. And the conclusion and recommendation were suited in the Chapter 4 of this paper.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were compiled, sorted, organized and tabulated. The data were subjected to statistical treatment to answer the questions proposed in the study. The statistical tools utilized were descriptive statistics, comparative, correlation and frequency count and percentage.

Descriptive Statistics. The mean of the data was set to determine the level of nationalism among Senior High School students and its relationship to their attitude towards history.

Table 3. Descriptive Interpretation for the Level of Nationalism

<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
4.00-3.50	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.49-2.50	Agree	High
2.49-1.50	Disagree	Low
1.49-1.00	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 3 is used in determining the descriptive interpretation of the respondents' level of nationalism.

Table 4. Descriptive Interpretation for the Level of Attitude towards History

<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
4.00-3.50	Strongly Agree	Very Favorable
3.49-2.50	Agree	Favorable
2.49-1.50	Disagree	Unfavorable
1.49-1.00	Strongly Disagree	Very Unfavorable

Table 4 is used in determining the descriptive interpretation of the respondents' level of attitude towards history.

Inferential Statistics. T-test was used to assess the significant difference of the respondents' sex and grade level of the respondents between their levels of nationalism and attitude towards history. One way- ANOVA was used for the significant difference between the strand and ethnicity of the respondents in terms of the levels of nationalism and attitude towards history. Pearson's r Correlation was utilized to compute for the significant relationship between the levels of nationalism and attitude towards history.

Thematic analysis was used in interpreting the qualitative data through identifying appropriate themes of the listed ways in strengthening one's sense of nationalism.

Results and Discussion

This chapter shows the data gathered from the 389 students of Saint Mary's University Senior High School. The results collected were analyzed through Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The sections below present the structure of specific research problems about the Level of Nationalism of SHS students and its relationship to their level of attitude towards History.

Level of Nationalism among Senior High School students and their Attitude towards History

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of the Level of Nationalism of the Respondents

	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
National Pride			
I enjoy reading about Philippine Nationalism because it gives me a sense of pride in my country.	3.06	.69	High
Talking to people about the Philippines gives me a feeling of pride in my country.	3.22	.61	High
I attend big Philippine event/s to support my country.	2.70	.71	High
I am proud to be a Filipino.	3.14	.66	High
I prefer products that are made in the Philippines.	3.04	.68	High
Supporting my country is the main reason I follow all the rules.	3.13	.67	High
I feel proud when I sing Lupang Hinirang song.	3.37	.64	High
I have a national flag prominently displayed in my home and my car during National Day.	2.52	.95	High
I will not pay more for a product because it was made in the Philippines.	2.63	.82	High

The interests of my country come before all other nations, including those that are in desperate needs.	2.95	.70	High
I enjoy talking about Nationalism because it makes me proud of my country.	3.01	.68	High
Attending the National Day in my country gives me a chance to show my national pride.	3.02	.67	High
I enjoy reading about Philippine nationalism because it gives me a sense of pride in my country.	3.06	.67	High
Watching something that relates with nationalism gives me a feeling of national pride that I do not get from any other activity.	3.16	.66	High
Connection to Countrymen			
Watching the Philippine event/s give/s me a sense of connection with my fellow countrymen.	3.22	.61	High
Talking about the Philippine event/s give/s me a sense of solidarity with my countrymen.	3.16	.65	High
The Philippines is the best country in the world to live in.	2.73	.96	High
I own Philippine clothing and I wear it proudly.	3.05	.73	High
My nation is the core of my collective identity.	3.08	.66	High
Talking about the Philippines with my countrymen didn't give me a feeling of national unity.	2.51	.84	High
I am a loyal fan of the national team whether they win or lose.	3.14	.73	High
National Belonging			
Watching the Philippine event/s provide/s a sense of national belonging to my nation.	3.24	.62	High
Reading about my country provide/s a sense of belonging to my nation.	3.15	.64	High
Talking about my country with others provide/s a sense of belonging to my nation.	3.16	.65	High
Attending a Philippine event reinforces my national identity.	3.08	.68	High
I have a strong sense of belonging to my country	3.15	.67	High
National interests are not more important than international interests.	2.68	.89	High
I am a Filipino and proud to be in the Philippines.	3.30	.70	High
Overall Mean	3.03	.71	High

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Very Low); 1.50-2.49 (Low); 2.50-3.49 (High); 3.50-4.00 (Very High)

Table 5 presents the result on the respondents' level of nationalism. 14 statements were adapted for national pride, seven for connection to countrymen, and seven for national belonging. There are a total of 28 statements with four scales each given to 389 respondents. Based on the results of the respondents' national pride, with Mean= 3.47 and SD=0.66, they agreed that they are proud to be Filipino. Moreover, the respondents felt a sense of connection with their fellow countrymen through watching Philippine events (M=3.23, SD=0.61). Furthermore, the respondents sensed their national belonging through being Filipino and residing in the country- Philippines (M=3.31, SD= 0.70). Additionally, the respondents felt their belonging every time they declare that they are Filipino and reside in the Philippines (Mean=3.31, SD = .70). Overall, the mean achieved (M= 3.03, SD= 0.71) was interpreted as high on the respondents' level of nationalism.

This implies that the Senior High School students of Saint Mary's University have a high level of nationalism in terms of pride, connection to fellow Filipinos and belonging. This denotes that the respondents are more connected towards other Filipinos through watching Philippine events. It also states that supporting the country's native products helps to boost national pride. Further, it demonstrates their loyalty to the country by being Filipino and living in the Philippines.

In recent years there has been an increasing focus on Filipino pride and celebrating national identity. Supporting local businesses and industries has become essential in this endeavor, as they make up a significant part of the economic landscape within the region through investing money into these companies or buying products made locally, Filipinos can ensure that their contributions are helping to create jobs and stimulate growth in various sectors. Furthermore, participating in initiatives such as Barangay Micro Business Enterprises (BMBEs) can provide even more benefit to those involved while also showing commitment to one's homeland. It is clear then that demonstrating patriotism through support of local businesses and industries should be considered a priority for all citizens of the Philippines. By doing so, not only would individuals be contributing positively towards their own livelihoods but also sending out a message about what it means to be truly patriotic (Pineda, 2023).

Table 6 illustrates the result of the respondents' level of attitude towards history. 12 statements with four scales each were given to the respondents. As stated from the results, the respondents pondered to learn the history of the country (M=3.20, SD= 0.69). The respondents also considered watching history channels and documentaries as a favorable attitude towards history (M=3.18, SD=0.76). However, only few respondents wanted to pursue a career in history (M=2.30, SD= 0.88) which signifies a negative attitude towards history. Generally, the mean attained (M=2.92, SD=0.80) was distinguished as favorable attitude towards history.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics of the Attitude of Senior High School students towards History

	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
I strongly like history.	3.05	.82	Favorable
I enjoy history class.	3.00	.81	Favorable
I strongly want to study history in my free time.	2.67	.86	Favorable
I find history a difficult subject.	2.84	.85	Favorable
I want to study history in higher classes/college.	2.63	.87	Favorable
I strongly want to pursue a career in history.	2.30	.89	Unfavorable
I strongly find studying history useful for present or future lives.	3.15	.68	Favorable
I strongly like to watch movies on historical themes.	3.11	.79	Favorable
I strongly want to know about the history of my country.	3.20	.70	Favorable
I strongly like to watch history channels or history documentaries.	3.18	.76	Favorable
I strongly want to take part in history-related activities such as debates, plays, history clubs, etc.	2.81	.90	Favorable
I strongly think history is a creative subject.	3.16	.74	Favorable
Overall Mean	2.92	.80	Favorable

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Very Low); 1.50-2.49 (Low); 2.50-3.49 (High); 3.50-4.00 (Very High)

This implies that watching documentaries and history channels is one of the positive attitudes the respondents have toward approaching History. Moreover, today’s generation is drawn to technological advancement which highly influences their attitude toward studying, understanding, and promoting one’s history. Documentary videos and channels tackled true and relevant stories which were highly regarded by many. However, it also says that there is a limited number of career takers in the discipline of history especially in the future.

Amengor (2007) stated in his research that when he worked with senior secondary school students, he found that the majority of students held a negative impression and perceptions about history. Students hold the misconception that history is a dead subject and of no use and one of the dullest subjects in school (Amengor, 2007). The responses highlighted that the students did not like history because they did not find it relevant and did not see any scope of studying history with future careers. The reason many students did not want to pursue history in higher classes was that they were not able to relate history with their lives, hence could not see it as a potential career choice (Issar, 2021).

Inferential Analysis between the Profile Variables and Level of Nationalism

Table 7. Comparison of the Level of Nationalism of the Respondents in Terms of Sex

	Male		Female		t(387)	p-value
Level of Nationalism	M	SD	M	SD	2.32	.021
	3.09	.42	3.00	.40		

*Significant (p<0.05)

Table 7 shows the comparison between the respondents’ level of nationalism and profile variable sex. For the T-test, t(387)= 2.32, p= .021, therefore, there is a significant difference between in the respondents’ level of nationalism in terms of their sex, which was determined by the Independent Samples T-test. Based on the result, male respondents have higher mean scores (M= 3.09, SD= .42) than female respondents (M= 3.00, SD= .40). Males tend to have higher levels of nationalism than females.

Oliveira (2014) stated that this may be due to several factors, including Socialization: Males are often socializing to be more competitive and assertive, which may translate into higher levels of nationalism; Testosterone: Testosterone is a hormone that is associated with aggression, dominance, and territoriality. Some studies have found that testosterone levels are correlated with nationalism, and Gender roles: In some societies, men are seen as the primary protectors of the nation. This may lead men to feel more responsible for and attached to their country.

Inglehart et al. (2005) posited that men were more likely than women to express national pride, to believe that their country is the best in the world, and to be willing to fight for their country. Furthermore, Esses et al. (2007) found that the relationship between sex and nationalism is complex and depends on several factors, such as the specific measure of nationalism used and the cultural context in which the study is conducted. The result of the current study revealed that, in general, men tend to express higher levels of nationalism than women.

Table 8 presents the comparison between the respondents’ level of nationalism and grade level (t(370) =2.57, p=.010) identified by the Independent Samples T-test. Results indicated that grade 11 students have higher levels of nationalism than grade 12 students (M= 3.09, 2.98, respectively) despite the increased number of respondents from the 12th grade. Hence, there is a significant difference between the respondent’s level of nationalism in terms of grade level.

Table 8. Comparison of the Level of Nationalism of the Respondents in Terms of Grade Level

Level of Nationalism	Grade 11		Grade 12		<i>t</i> (370)	<i>p</i> -value
	M	SD	M	SD		
	3.09	.43	2.98	.38	2.57	.010

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Durmaz et al. (2022) claimed that as the age and grade levels of the students increase, the number of concepts related to nationalism used by students increases. Nationalism is understood differently by male and female students. While female students emphasize the concepts of love and work, male students emphasize the concepts of protection and independence. (Kymlicka, 2001) also proposed that nationalism tends to increase with age. The study also found that nationalism is positively correlated with patriotism and civic engagement. Moreover, according to Green and Heath (2009), nationalism is often taught in schools through the curriculum, extracurricular activities, and school rituals. The study also found that nationalism can be a powerful force in shaping students' identities.

Table 9. Comparison of the Level of Nationalism of the Respondents in Terms of Strand

Level of Nationalism	Strands	<i>f</i>	Mean	SD	<i>F</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
Level of Nationalism	AT-ABM	57	3.08	.34	2.29	.046
	AD Track	25	2.88	.39		
	TVL- HE	21	2.98	.42		
	AT-HumSS	72	3.12	.44		
	TVL-ICT	25	3.14	.45		
	AT-STEM	189	3.00	.41		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 9 illustrates the association between the level of nationalism of the Senior High School students and the profile variable- strand. There is a significant difference between the respondents' strand and level of nationalism ($F(388) = 2.29, p = .046$) identified through the one-way ANOVA Test. From the results gathered, the mean scores for Academic Track strands' ABM, HUMSS, and STEM indicated a high level of nationalism ($M = 3.08, 3.12, 3.00$, respectively). In addition, strands under the Technical Vocational Livelihood Track such as HE and ICT and Arts and Design Track, also indicated a high level of nationalism among the respondents ($M = 2.98, 3.14, 2.88$, respectively). Moreover, there is a significant difference between the strand HumSS and Tract AD presented in the POST HOC with a mean score of .116.

However, existing research stated that students in STEM strands tend to have higher levels of nationalism than students in non-STEM strands. This may be due to several factors including Problem-solving skills: Students in STEM strands are often taught how to solve complex problems. This may help them to develop a stronger sense of national identity, as they learn to work together to overcome challenges; Patriotism: STEM education often emphasizes the importance of patriotism and civic engagement. This may lead students in STEM strands to feel more responsible for their country and to be more willing to promote its interests and Nationalism in STEM fields: STEM fields are often associated with national power and prestige. This may lead students in STEM strands to develop a stronger sense of nationalism, as they identify with their country's success in these fields.

Chen et al. (2015) explained that students in STEM strands tended to have higher levels of nationalism than students in non-STEM strands. The study also found that nationalism was positively correlated with science achievement. Moreover, Gaskell (2017) claimed that STEM education can help to promote positive attitudes towards science and technology. The study also found that STEM education can help to develop students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. This suggests that education could provide opportunities for improvements that can help all students develop a stronger and more balanced way of their nationalism. Furthermore, it might be beneficial to include activities that promote national awareness to strands with lower levels of nationalism in order to create unity among all students.

Table 10 presents the observation on SHS students' level of nationalism and their ethnicity. However, unlike the previous variables, there is no significant difference between the respondents' nationalism and ethnicity ($F = 288 = 1.26, p = .19$).

This implies that respondents may not consistently exhibit higher or lower levels of nationalism based solely on their ethnic background. The finding of independence between ethnicity and nationalism indicates that factors beyond cultural or ethnic origins, such as personal experiences or external influences, significantly shape individuals' nationalistic views. In essence, the relationship between nationalism and ethnicity is complex and not universally predictable, prompting further exploration into the diverse factors that contribute to the formation of national identity among respondents.

Pamir (n.d.) said that ethnicity becomes a form of nationalism when it assumes a political (and often territorial) dimension that challenges the status quo, and, in some cases, the legitimacy and stability of the state in question by becoming a catalyst for intra- or inter-state conflict. Some would argue that the most dynamic ingredient of nationalism is ethnicity; indeed, nationalism is in essence the political expression of ethnicity.

Table 10. Comparison of the Level of Nationalism of the Respondents in Terms of Ethnicity

	Ethnic Groups	f	Mean	SD	F- value	p- value
Level of Nationalism	Gaddang	13	3.00	.31	1.92	
	Ifugao	38	3.14	.38		
	Ilocano	159	3.03	.42		
	Isinay	3	3.06	.58		
	Tagalog	94	3.09	.42		
	Others	14	2.93	.30		
	Ilocano- Tagalog	34	2.81	.35		
	Gaddang- Tagalog-	1	2.83	-		
	Itawes	1	2.88	-		
	Ifugao- Ilocano- Tagalog	3	2.33	.04		
	Ilocano-Isinay	9	3.48	.32		
	Ifugao- Ilocano	1	3.15	-		
	Ifugao- Kankanaey	1	3.76	-		
	Ifugao- Bontoc	3	2.98	.19		
	Ilocano- Isinay- Tagalog	1	3.07	-		
	Ifugao- Ilocano-	2	3.14	.14		
	Tagalog- Bicolano	1	2.50	-		
	Gaddang- Ifugao-	2	3.00	.27		
	Ilocano- Tagalog	1	3.50	-		
	Ilocano- Waray	1	3.67	-		
	Ilocano- Isinay-	1	3.76	-		
	Pangasinense	2	3.65	.12		
	Gaddang- Ilocano-	4	2.96	.48		

*Not Significant ($p>0.05$)

Inferential Analysis between the Profile Variables and Level of Attitude towards History

Table 11. Comparison of the Level of Attitude towards History of the Respondents in Terms of Sex

	Male		Female		t(312.93)	p- value
Level of Attitude towards History	M	SD	M	SD	1.08	.283
History	2.96	.59	2.90	.49		

*Not Significant ($p>0.05$)

Table 11 illustrates the comparison of the respondents' sex and their level of attitude towards history. For the T-test, $t(312.93)=1.08$, $p=.283$, the result indicates that there is no significant difference between the respondents' level of attitude towards history in terms of sex which was determined by the Independent Samples T-test. Based on the result, male respondents have higher mean scores ($M=2.96$, $SD=.59$) than female respondents ($M=2.90$, $SD=.49$). This implies that the respondents' level of attitude is not significant with their sex.

Behar (2023) said that men are more interested in things and women are more interested in people. Angyal (2018) stated that history is still a story that's largely told by men, in an analysis of America's most popular recent history books found that the vast majority — 75.8 percent — were written by men. Most of those men wrote about other men: 71.7 percent of biographies were about male subjects. Many women who wrote biographies — 31 percent — wrote about men, too, while only 6 percent of male biographers chose to document a woman's life (Angyal, 2018).

Table 12 shows the comparison of Grade 11 and Grade 12 students and their level of attitude towards history ($t(387)=1.87$, $p\text{-value}=.062$). The mean values indicate that, 11th grade students have a more favorable attitude ($M=2.97$) compared to 12th grade students ($M=2.87$) in measuring their level of attitude towards history. The result indicates that there is no significant difference in the respondents' grade level and level of attitude towards history.

Table 12. Comparison of the Level of Attitude towards History of the Respondents in Terms of Grade Level

	Grade 11		Grade 12		t(387)	p- value
Level of Attitude towards History	M	SD	M	SD	1.87	.062
History	2.97	.53	2.87	.53		

*Not Significant ($p>0.05$)

Schick (1991) claimed that students either have negative feelings about history or they are neutral about it. Schug (1982) found that social science was ranked as one of the least favorite subjects, ranked by a grade 6 to 12 students which were based on the skills needed

for future career. Amengor (2007) initiated that majority of senior high school students hold a negative impression and perceptions about history. Ahmad et al. (2016) examined the attitude of students toward social science and claimed that students were more interested in studying natural science subjects as it could get them attractive and high paying jobs. Boadu (2016) conducted an empirical study in Ghana on 32 history teachers and 18 senior high school students and concluded that teachers and students struggled with overloaded syllabus; insufficient teaching resources and lack of academic support made teaching and studying history a challenge for the teachers and students respectively.

Table 13. Comparison of the Level of Attitude towards History of the Respondents in Terms of Strand

	Strands	f	Mean	SD	F- value	p- value
Level of Attitude towards History	AT-ABM	57	2.77	.46	3.51	.004
	AD Track	25	2.79	.54		
	TVL- HE	21	2.95	.54		
	AT-HumSS	72	3.08	.51		
	TVL-ICT	25	3.14	.51		
	AT-STEM	189	2.89	.55		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 13 presents a comparison of level of attitudes towards history in terms of strands. The results of the One-Way ANOVA indicate a significant difference in respondents' level attitudes based on their chosen strand/track ($F(388) = 3.51, p = .004$). Further analysis reveals that the mean scores for Academic Track Strands, namely ABM, STEM, and HumSS, reflect a favorable level of attitude ($M = 2.77, 2.89, 3.08$), respectively. Similarly, Technical Vocational Livelihood Track Strands- HE, and ICT, including Arts and Design Track also indicate a favorable level of attitude among the respondents ($M = 2.95, 3.14, 2.79$), respectively. Moreover, the POST HOC Analysis highlights significant difference between specific academic strands. Notably, there is a significant difference in their level of attitude between ABM and HumSS ($p = .013$), as well as ABM and ICT ($p = .046$).

The result implies that the respondents' level of attitude towards history differ significantly depending on their strands/track. The high mean scores across multiple strands suggest a positive attitude toward the subject-history. The differences observe between specific strands, such as ABM and HumSS and ICT, indicate that certain academic tracks have different views or approaches in the study of history.

Issar (2021) discovers that most students focusing on science and math- oriented subjects exhibit an unfavorable attitude or lack of interest toward history. The study suggests that the content in history classes may be a contributing factor to students' negative attitudes. The linear approach to teaching history is seen as a potential cause for the subject appearing dull, monotonous, and burdensome to students.

Table 14. Comparison of the Level of Attitude towards History of the Respondents in Terms of Ethnicity

	Ethnic Groups	f	Mean	SD	F- value	p- value
Level of Nationalism	Gaddang	13	3.29	.50	1.12	0.32
	Ifugao	38	2.83	.51		
	Ilocano	159	2.91	.52		
	Isinay	3	2.61	.46		
	Tagalog	94	2.88	.60		
	Others	14	3.13	.44		
	Ilocano- Tagalog	34	3.03	.45		
	Gaddang- Tagalog-	1	2.83	-		
	Itawes	1	2.92	-		
	Ifugao- Ilocano- Tagalog	3	2.50	.00		
	Ilocano-Isinay	9	2.86	.64		
	Ifugao- Ilocano	1	2.50	-		
	Ifugao- Kankanaey	1	3.08	-		
	Ifugao- Bontoc	13	3.29	.50		
	Ilocano- Isinay- Tagalog	3	4.00	-		
	Ifugao- Ilocano-	1	2.88	1.12		
	Tagalog- Bicolano	2	2.83	-		
	Gaddang- Ifugao-	1	2.50	.59		
	Ilocano- Tagalog	2	2.92	-		
	Ilocano- Waray	1	3.50	-		
	Ilocano- Isinay-	1	3.58	-		
Pangasinense	1	3.25	.59			
Gaddang- Ilocano-	4	2.81	.20			

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 14 presents the results of the comparison of the respondents' ethnicity and level of attitude towards history. Likewise, there is no significant difference of the respondents' ethnicity and their level of attitude towards history. Based on the table, the result indicates a mean score ($F(388) = 1.12, p = 0.32$). This suggests that despite the respondents' varied cultural backgrounds, they all arrived at the same or, more likely, a similar attitude towards history, implying the converge challenges the idea that cultural differences inevitably can lead even to one's attitude on historical events and narratives and raises the possibility that some aspects of historical attitude may be universal or shared across cultural diversity.

According to Twala (2005), the use of historical exhibition as a means of presenting history across class and racial-ethnic lines can be nurtured. Historical exhibitions are taking a number of approaches, all of which are at least implicitly political. Some exhibitions dramatized the oppression of apartheid, to the discomfort of those who want to forget. Apart from the exhibitions, a large number of people are actively involved or interested in creating and popularizing a diverse history which should be the center of curriculum at school level (Twala, 2005).

Inferential Analysis between Level of Nationalism and Level of Attitude towards History

Table 15. Correlation between Level of Nationalism and Attitude towards History

	<i>Pearson's r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>QD</i>
Level of Nationalism			Moderately High
—	.60**	.000	Correlation
Level of Attitude towards History			

Table 15 presents the statistical analysis of the relationship between respondents' level of nationalism and their level of attitude towards history. Pearson's r correlation coefficient is used to measure the strength and direction of the relationship. In this case, the coefficient is 0.60, indicating a moderately high correlation. This signifies that a person with nationalist views tends to know their history more. Moreover, nationalism in the view of history is the center of societal unity in shared practices, traditions, beliefs, language, and culture.

Andrews et al. (2010) stated that different measures of national pride and shame may also influence different measures of attitudes toward history, and their impact may be either stronger or weaker than the variables included in this model. Moreover, the author illustrated that the social and political achievements of the UK are associated with a more liberal view of the history curriculum, while pride in sporting and economic achievements is associated with a more authoritarian view. Likewise, militarist sources of national pride are correlated with a traditional view of history, while radical political sources are correlated with a multicultural view. Students' attitudes towards history therefore appear to be loading onto two distinct factors, which we have termed: traditional/conservative and multicultural/liberal. These two approaches to the study of history broadly reflect the polarized views of education that have characterized the 'culture wars' in multicultural Western societies (Evans, 1997).

Qualitative Analysis

Table 16 displays the result of the thematic analysis of the responses of the respondents about the ways to strengthen a sense of nationalism among the youth with a total of six themes. Specifically, the majority of the respondents answered that nourishing one's sense of nationalism was in his/her patriotic sentiments. The devotion, loyalty, and sense of pride of an individual to his country reflect this theme. Embracing one's culture, tradition, and beliefs and being Makabansa are examples of exemplifying a patriotic desire.

Moreover, 108 responses were gathered saying that history plays a big role in strengthening a sense of nationalism, especially as knowledge. Reading historical books, watching historical events and documentaries, and listening to stories from key informants about the country are the quotes under this theme.

Table 16. Thematic Analysis of Ways in Strengthening a Sense of Nationalism among the Youths

<i>Sense of Nationalism</i>	<i>Example Statements</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Patriotic Sentiments	Be proud of your country. As a Marian student I strengthen my sense of nationalism by honoring and respecting our culture. By embracing what is ours and not ignoring the beauty of our given culture. Making proud of our country by knowing the history of the Philippines, giving attention to the activities and events supporting every Filipino who represents the country because it is a way to strengthen the sense of nationalism. Paying attention to the resources and materials. By letting other people realize that having a sense of nationalism doesn't necessarily mean blindly supporting the government but having a sense of pride in what our country; people had done/is doing/will do. To be more makabansa and to learn to accept and love our country. As a Marian student, I can strengthen my sense of nationalism by using Filipino language to interact with others in my daily life. Treasuring The	128	37.21

	language and passing it to the next generation, purchasing local goods such as Filipino foods and souvenirs from multiple locations here in the Philippines and by respecting my fellow Filipinos and of course our flag.		
History	As a Marian student, I think reading and watching histories can strengthen our sense of nationalism for us to be aware of what happened in the past. As a Marian student, learn more about the beauties of our country, find out more about its people and culture then you'll see that there is more to it. That there is more to being a Filipino. Read about History that would give them understanding and knowledge, to be proud that they are to be Pinoy, in a way that they know how Filipinos fought for their country. By giving examples and past instances of Philippine patriotism to lift the people's sense of nationalism. I will suggest that you should hear from your lolas and lolos so you should know more about your sense of nationalism.	108	31.40
Campaign Towards Nationalism	Having exposure to nationalistic ideals and providing more events and activities that would promote nationalism. A way to strengthen nationalism would be to put emphasis on being an activity contributing Filipino citizens. By doing this, those who are active contributors to the country will be honored by the recognition, and perhaps those who are not will be inspired to follow. As a Marian student, joining clubs such as the kamalayan club to strengthen and broaden our knowledge of our nation.	36	10.47
Supporting Domestic/Locally Made Products	Acknowledge our own products and learn about our history. Use local brands to expose them to others. We should choose to buy Philippine-made products instead of investing in Foreign-Country products that are mostly made out of chemicals and uses animal tester.	29	8.43
Respect for National Symbol	My suggestion would be to always respect the singing of the National Hymn (Lupang Hinirang). Yes. I think one of the ways to strengthen our sense of nationalism is by having at least one flag ceremony each month. The most basic suggestion that I can suggest is to sing the national anthem with pride.	28	8.14
Education	SMU as an institution should collaborate with historians and make handbooks containing pre-colonial history and colonial history. Finding ways to change corrupted systems in the country. (i. e. Lessening school hours & stress for students for more enhanced learning.) Return the (AP) Araling Panlipunan subject in the DepEd curriculum.	15	4.36
Total		344	100.00%

As suggested from the result, campaigning towards nationalism like joining clubs, promoting different cultures through various activities, and exposing himself/herself to the ideals of nationalism is also vital in heightening nationalism among the youth. Furthermore, showing loyalty to the country through supporting the country's own products and pledging allegiance to the Philippine flag is an active way of establishing a sense of national consciousness. In terms of Education, a curriculum development was proposed by the respondents. Enhancing the educational system, bringing back the Araling Panlipunan subject in the DepEd curriculum, and collaborating with the institution to historians were some of the proposed developments from the respondents.

Mokhtar et al. (2016) stated that the spirit of nationalism needs to be instilled into the young generations from the beginning. As a developing country, the government needs to emphasize the spirit of nationalism in order to ensure that important state histories are remembered as Malaysia enters its modern era. This study focused on a class of young generations who will shape the future state. Nationalism in a special sense reflects the spirit of the desire and the ability to fight for a change, especially in dignity and contributing to a sovereign nation. Therefore, this spirit can be achieved when all members of a nation can appreciate the true sense of 'independence'.

Conclusions

Nationalism caters to the home rule of a country. It is not an ideology but a sense of belonging to one's country. Oftentimes, history develops one's nationalism through history-related lessons and patriotic sentiments toward historical places, people, and products.

This study delved into the perceived level of nationalism among Senior High School students at Saint Mary's University and its relationship to their attitudes toward history. The research encompassed statistical and thematic analyses of the respondents' perceptions, providing valuable insights into the multi-faceted aspects of nationalism. The research was a combination of quantitative

research (designs: descriptive-comparative and descriptive- correlational) and qualitative research with a total of 389 respondents from different strands, sexes, ethnicities, and grade levels.

The results of the study reveal that the students exhibited a high level of nationalism, particularly in their national pride, connection to countrymen, and sense of national belonging. Their strong sense of national pride was evident in their identity and their pride towards the country, supporting it even in their choice of products and patriotic sentiments towards the country. The study also highlighted the role of history in fostering nationalism, emphasizing the importance of understanding the country's past and the sacrifices made for its freedom.

Moreover, there is a significant difference found in the respondents' level of nationalism and profile variables such as sex, strand, and grade level. However, there was no significant difference in nationalism based on ethnicity, for nationality and ethnicity are united towards each other. In addition, a significant difference was found between the respondents' level of attitude towards history and strands. Nonetheless, there is no significant difference in the comparison of the respondents' level of attitude toward history in terms of sex, grade level, and ethnicity.

Furthermore, the research uncovered a moderately high relationship between the students' level of nationalism and their level of attitude towards history. Those who exhibited a stronger sense of nationalism tended to have a more positive attitude toward history. This suggests that cultivating a sense of nationalism can be an effective way to encourage an interest in history among students.

The qualitative analysis provided additional insights into ways of strengthening a sense of nationalism among the youth, including emphasizing the importance of history, embracing patriotic sentiments, supporting domestic products, and education, showing respect to the National symbols, and promoting campaigns towards nationalism.

In a world where globalization and modernization often challenge traditional values and national identity, fostering a strong sense of nationalism among the youth is of paramount importance. Therefore, this research served as a valuable contribution to understanding how to instill a sense of pride, loyalty, and appreciation for one's country, while also underlining the pivotal role that history plays in this endeavor. By implementing the suggestions and recommendations gathered from the respondents, educational institutions and policymakers can work towards nurturing a more patriotic and informed generation.

The findings of this study indulge several recommendations. First, to practice monthly flag-raising ceremonies and to recite the patriotic oath which may increase the Filipinos' sense of nationalism. For educators, to integrate history-related topics in the subjects under the core curriculum of all strands in Senior High School.

Finally, future researchers, to conduct further studies focusing on the youths' nationalism and their interest in history as a school subject and future job. Moreover, conduct further yet separate studies about nationalism and ethnicity; nationalism and gender; nationalism and bachelor's degree; nationalism and employment; and nationalism and age (according to its range). Furthermore, this study is a basis for reconsidering returning history subjects in the education system of the country especially in Senior High School to strengthen the sense of nationalism among the youths.

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